

2,4-Dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime as an Extraction Photometric Reagent for the Simultaneous Estimation of Copper and Nickel†

M. J. EAPEN, C. S. DORAI and P. UMAPATHY*

Inorganic Chemistry Division, National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-411 008

Manuscript received 3 October, 1989, revised 29 August 1990, accepted 12 October 1990

2,4-Dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenone oxime has been used as an extraction photometric reagent for the determination of microgram quantities of copper in the presence of Ni^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III} and Pb^{II} by extracting its complex using tartrate or diethylamine at pH 8.5–9.0. Microgram quantities of nickel were also determined in the presence of Fe^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} and Pb^{II} using hydroxylamine hydrochloride or diethylamine. The reagent could also be used for the simultaneous extraction photometric determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}.

THE study of *o*-hydroxyarylketones and their oximes as analytical reagents has been confined chiefly to *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and its oxime¹. However, the potential of substituted-*o*-hydroxyacetophenones and their oximes as analytical reagents has not been investigated to any great extent. The synthesis and use of the reagents, 2,4-dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenone, 3,5-dibromo-2,4-dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenone and their oximes with diethylamine as synergist in the extraction and separation of metals has been reported earlier by us². 2,4-Dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenone oxime can be used for extraction photometric determination of microgram quantities of copper or nickel in a variety of samples. Furthermore, the reagent could be used for the simultaneous determination of copper and nickel. The tolerance levels of several cations and anions in the analysis have also been studied.

Experimental

The preparation of the reagents, 2,4-dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime (DMHAO) and 3,5-dibromo-2,4-dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime (DBDMHAO) has been described earlier². A 1% solution of the reagent in ethanol was used. The metal ion solutions were prepared by dissolving pure metals (99.999% purity) in perchloric acid and diluted with deionised water to obtain 1 mmol solutions. A 1.0 M sodium perchlorate solution was used to adjust the ionic strength. Aqueous diethylamine solution (1 : 1) was used. Chloroform was used as the solvent of extraction. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. A Radiometer PHM 63 digital pH meter and a Pye-Unicam SP-8-1900 atomic absorption spectrophotometer were used.

An aliquot containing the metal ion (Cu or Ni, 10–65 µg), the reagent (2.5 ml) and sodium per-

chlorate (2 ml) was taken and its pH was adjusted with sodium hydroxide solution to 5.0–9.5 for copper estimation (pH 8.5–10.5 for nickel). The metal complexes were extracted with chloroform (10 ml). The extract of the copper complex was green ($\lambda_{\max}$ 336 nm) and that of the nickel was dull red ($\lambda_{\max}$ 364 nm); the colours of the CHCl₃ extracts were stable for a week. The absorbance of the extracts was measured using a Pye-Unicam SP-8-100 UV/VIS spectrophotometer. Copper or nickel estimations in presence of other metal ions or in alloys, ores and in spent-catalysts were carried out using a masking agent, tartrate or a reducing agent, hydroxylamine hydrochloride at pHs mentioned in Tables 1 and 2 and after extraction into CHCl₃, the absorbance measurements were carried out.

Results and Discussion

The reagent, DMHAO has been found useful for extraction and determination of copper from

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF COPPER FROM SOLUTIONS CONTAINING OTHER METAL IONS USING DMHAO

Cu taken µg	Cu found µg	Error %	Interfering metal ion (molar ratio, times)	Masking agent added (g)	pH of extraction
50.84	50.70	0.27	—	—	5.0
63.54	63.15	0.61	—	—	5.0
63.54	63.40	0.22	Ni ^{II} (100)	Tartrate (0.5)	8.5
50.84	50.47	0.72	Fe ^{III} (100)	Tartrate (0.5)	8.5
50.84	50.90	0.11	Al ^{III} (100)	Tartrate (0.5)	8.5
63.54	63.88	0.53	Zn ^{II} (1000)	—	5.0
63.54	62.97	0.90	Cr ^{III} (5)	Diethylamine ^a	9.0
50.84	51.24	0.79	Pb ^{II} (50)	—	5.0

^aSynergist.

† N. C. I. Communication No. 4708.

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF NICKEL FROM SOLUTIONS CONTAINING OTHER METAL IONS USING DMHAO

Ni taken μg	Ni found μg	$E_{\text{error}} \%$	Interfering metal ions (molar ratio, times)	Reducing agent (g)	pH of extraction
58.7	58.4	0.51	—	—	8.5
35.1	35.1	0.00	—	—	8.5
46.9	46.4	1.06	Fe^{III} (100)	Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.25)	8.7
58.7	58.3	0.68	Zn^{II} (1000)	—	8.7
29.3	29.25	0.34	Cd^{II} (50)	—	8.5
46.9	47.3	0.85	Al^{III} (50)	—	8.5
58.7	58.88	0.20	Cr^{III} (5)	Diethylamine ^a	9.0
46.9	47.16	0.55	Pb^{II} (50)	—	5.0

^aSynergist

Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Al^{III} , Cr^{III} and Pb^{II} ; and nickel from Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Al^{III} , Cr^{III} and Pb^{II} (Tables 1 and 2). Table 3 shows the molar absorptivities of the

 TABLE 3—VALUES OF λ_{max} AND MOLAR ABSORBANCES OF METAL COMPLEXES OF DMHAO AND DBDMHAO

Metal	DMHAO		DBDMHAO	
	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_M $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ (± 100)	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_M $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ (± 100)
Cu^{II}	336	7300	350	7700
Ni^{II}	364	6200	372	7800
Co^{II}	338	7700	356	10500
Fe^{III}	334	5080	336	10600
Mn^{II}	342	6250	346	7800

The copper complex of DBDMHAO is extractable only in presence of diethylamine^a

metal complexes of the DMHAO and DBDMHAO. The copper and nickel complexes of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime³ have an ϵ_M of around 3.0×10^3 to $4.0 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. It is observed that the introduction of two bromine atoms in the aromatic nucleus leads to increase in the ϵ_M of the complexes of all the metals. The chloroform extract of the

complexes of DMHAO obeys Beer's law in the range 0.5–7.5 ppm. For complete extraction the reagent concentration needs to be only 10 times that of the metal. This reagent could be used for the determination of copper in different samples by measuring the absorbance at 336 nm (Table 4). The main interfering elements are manganese, iron, nickel, cobalt and chromium. While iron, nickel and cobalt could be masked by the addition of excess of sodium tartrate, manganese has to be removed as MnO_2 by boiling the sample solution with sodium chlorate and nitric acid. The interference of chromium is overcome by the addition of diethylamine. The values obtained for nickel in different samples by measuring the absorbance at 364 nm are given in Table 4. The large amount of iron (80.62%) in stainless steel was removed by ether extraction in HCl medium prior to the extraction of nickel. Traces of iron and copper could be masked by adding hydroxylamine hydrochloride and thiosulphate into the sample solution respectively.

The reagent can also be used for the simultaneous determination of copper and nickel by measuring the absorbances at 336 nm (λ_{max} of copper complex) and 364 nm (λ_{max} of nickel complex). The amounts of the metals in the extract were found (Table 5) from the equations,

$$\text{Ni} = \frac{A_{364} \epsilon_{\text{Cu}} - A_{336} \epsilon_{\text{Ni}}}{\epsilon_{\text{Ni}} \epsilon_{\text{Cu}} - \epsilon_{\text{Ni}} \epsilon_{\text{Cu}}} \times 0.587 \text{ g}$$

$$\text{Cu} = \frac{A_{336} \epsilon_{\text{Ni}} - A_{364} \epsilon_{\text{Cu}}}{\epsilon_{\text{Ni}} \epsilon_{\text{Cu}} - \epsilon_{\text{Ni}} \epsilon_{\text{Cu}}} \times 0.635 \text{ g}$$

where A_{336} and A_{364} are the absorbances of the sample extract at 336 and 364 nm and ϵ values are the molar absorptivities for the nickel and copper complexes of DMHAO. It is observed that the interference of Fe^{III} could be suppressed by hydroxylamine hydrochloride and the interference of Cr^{III} be eliminated by the addition of diethylamine. All the experiments were performed with synthetic mixtures. The results of analysis of some commercially available samples are given in Table 4. The

TABLE 4—ESTIMATION OF METALS IN SAMPLES USING DMHAO

Sample	Copper		Nickel	
	% Reported	% Found	% Reported	% Found
Silver	0.0055	0.0054	—	—
6% Si-Al alloy ^a	0.295	0.292	—	—
Zinc concentrate ^a	0.132	0.133	—	—
85% aluminium alloy ^a	2.48	2.46	—	—
Iron pyrites	2.73	2.70	—	—
Catalyst spent mass	9.97	10.07	—	—
Brass	57.80	57.70	—	—
Aluminium bronze	72.00	71.82	—	—
Stainless steel (20 1) ^a	—	—	6.63	6.57
Ni/Cd solid solution	—	—	1.0	0.99
Thin film (μg)	—	—	50.2	50.5
34-a-steel acid open hearth ^a	0.222	0.225	0.232	0.229
Monel	32.83	32.63	64.08	64.57

^aNBS sample

TABLE 5—SIMULTANEOUS EXTRACTION PHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Cu^{II} AND Ni^{II} USING DMHAO

Sl. no.	Cu			Ni		
	Taken μg	Found μg	Error %	Taken μg	Found μg	Error %
1.	50.8	51.0	0.4	46.9	46.6	0.6
2.	12.7	12.6	0.8	58.7	58.6	0.2
3.	25.4	25.6	0.8	29.3	29.4	0.3
4.	38.1	38.3	0.5	17.6	17.4	1.1
5.	31.8	31.9	0.3	23.5	23.7	0.9
6.	18.9	18.7	1.0	11.7	11.8	0.9
7.	15.8	15.7	0.6	14.7	14.8	0.7
8.	18.9	19.1	1.1	11.7	11.6	0.9
9 ^a	50.8	50.7	0.2	35.1	34.9	0.6
10 ^b	63.5	63.1	0.6	58.7	58.2	0.9

^aIn the presence of Fe^{III} (56 μg).^bIn the presence of Cr^{III} (500 μg).

values reported in all the above analyses are the average of 3 to 5 determinations. The likely interferences of various ions in the analysis of Cu, 63.54 μg and Ni, 58.69 μg using this reagent are as follows: for Cu: sodium, potassium, ammonium, chloride, nitrate, chlorate, tartrate, NH₂OH ($3 \times 10^6 \mu\text{g}$); Sr^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, acetate, carbonate, bicarbonate, oxalate, sulphate, bromide, fluoride ($1 \times 10^6 \mu\text{g}$); Ba^{II}, Ca^{II}, Mo^{VI}, vanadate, Bi^{III}, Ag^I, Al^{III}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, phosphate, thiocyanate ($1-5 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}$); Sn^{II}, Ti^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Sn^{IV}, Cr^{III}, thiosulphate,

cyanide, citrate ($1 \times 10^2 \mu\text{g}$); and for Ni: Na, K, Mg^{II}, chloride, nitrate, sulphate, chlorate, bromide, acetate, Zn^{II}, Sr^{II}, NH₂OH, carbonate, bicarbonate, (1 to $3 \times 10^6 \mu\text{g}$); fluoride, thiocyanate, Mo^{VI}, Ca^{II}, Ag^I, Ba^{II} (1 to $5 \times 10^5 \mu\text{g}$); Pb^{II}, thiosulphate, Al^{III}, Cd^{II}, phosphate, Bi^{III}, V^V (1 to $3 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}$); Ti^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Sn^{II} (1 to $10^3 \mu\text{g}$) and Cr^{III}, Sn^{IV}, citrate, oxalate, cyanide (1 to $10^2 \mu\text{g}$). Since it is found from the preliminary spectrophotometric determination studies that DBDMHAO is similar to DMHAO, not much attention is given to its application in the determination of metals.

Stoichiometry of the metal complexes was confirmed by the study of the variation of log *D* vs pH as well as log *D* vs log *L* curves (*D* = distribution ratio and *L* = ligand concentration). The log *D* vs pH plots of Cu^{II}-DMHAO and Ni^{II}-DMHAO complexes show slopes of 1.96 and 1.83 respectively. Similarly, the slopes of log *D* vs log *L* plots are also found to be around 2.0.

References

1. T. S. REDDY and S. B. RAO, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 968.
2. M. J. EAPEN, C. S. DORAI and V. DAMODARAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 1022.
3. T. S. REDDY and S. B. RAO, *Curr. Sci.*, 1979, **48**, 439.